

THE
ARANEIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA
Part 3 Ne-U

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ARANEIDAE PART 3 - CONTENTS

NEOSCONA Simon, 1864	3
• <i>Neoscona alberti</i> (Strand, 1913).....	4
• <i>Neoscona angulatula</i> (Schenkel, 1937).....	5
• <i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885).....	6-7
• <i>Neoscona chiarinii</i> (Pavesi, 1883).....	8
• <i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844).....	9
• <i>Neoscona kivuensis</i> Grasshoff, 1986.....	10
• <i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863).....	11-12
• <i>Neoscona novella</i> (Simon, 1907).....	13
• <i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879).....	14
• <i>Neoscona quadrigibbosa</i> Grasshoff, 1986.....	15
• <i>Neoscona quincasea</i> Roberts, 1983.....	16
• <i>Neoscona rapta</i> (Thorell, 1899).....	17
• <i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858).....	18-19
• <i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837).....	20-22
• <i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910).....	23
• <i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864).....	24-25
• <i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall, 1865).....	26
NEPHILINGIS Kuntner, 2013	27
• <i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	28
PARALARINIA Grasshoff, 1970	29
• <i>Paralarinia bartelsi</i> (Lessert, 1933).....	30
PARAPLECTANA Brito Capello, 1867	31
• <i>Paraplectana thorntoni</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	32
• <i>Paraplectana walleri</i> (Blackwall, 1865).....	33
• Undetermined species.....	34
PARARANEUS Caporiacco, 1940	35
• <i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898).....	36-37
• <i>Pararaneus perforatus</i> (Thorell, 1899).....	38
• <i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885).....	39
• Undetermined species.....	40
PASILOBUS Simon, 1895	41
• <i>Pasilobus dippenarae</i> Roff & Haddad, 2015.....	42
POLTYS C. L. Koch, 1843	43
• <i>Poltys furcifer</i> Simon, 1881	44
PRASONICA Simon, 1895	45
• <i>Prasonica albolimbata</i> Simon, 1895	46
• <i>Prasonica nigrotaeniata</i> (Simon, 1909)	47
• <i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895.....	48
PYCNACANTHA Blackwall, 1865	49
• <i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781).....	50-51
• Undetermined species.....	52
SINGA C. L. Koch, 1836	53
• <i>Singa albodorsata</i> Kauri, 1950.....	54
• <i>Singa lawrencei</i> (Lessert, 1930).....	55
SINGAFROTYPA Benoit, 1962	56
• <i>Singafrotypa mandela</i> Kuntner & Hormiga, 2002.....	57
TRICHONEPHILA Leach, 1815	58
• <i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859.....	59-60
• <i>Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis</i> (Vinson, 1863).....	61
• <i>Trichonephila komaci</i> Kuntner & Coddington 2009.....	62
• <i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859).....	63-64
URSA Simon, 1895	65
• <i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895.....	66
• Undetermined species.....	67
ZYGIELLA F.P.-Cambridge, 1902	68 NEW
REFERENCES	66-71

GENUS *NEOSCONA* Simon, 1864

The genus *Neoscona* described by Simon (1864) is known from 116 species and 11 subspecies with a world-wide distribution. Seventeen species have been recorded from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Neoscona Hairy Field Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Neoscona arabesca* (Walckenaer, 1841)

MORPHOLOGY: Spiders of this genus are small to medium in size. The females are usually larger than the males. The colour varies from cream to brown to greyish black with a distinct abdominal pattern in many species allowing the spider to blend in with the environment when resting. Presence of longitudinal thoracic groove in female separates *Neoscona* from all members of the genus *Araneus*. Median ocular quadrangle forming a trapezium that is slightly longer than wide; anterior medians largest or subequal to the posterior medians; lateral eyes close and not situated on prominent tubercles, posterior laterals smallest; both rows of eyes recurved. In males coxa I ventrally provided with a hook on the distal rim; tibia II having macrosetae (spines) on prolateral surface. Abdomen may be oval, sub oval, triangular or sub-triangular in shape. Epigyne is a simple tongue like; scape completely fused to the base and provided with one or two pairs of lateral lobes; epigynal openings situated underneath of scape. Palpal patella of male provided with two strong, curved and long spines.

LIFESTYLE: Orb-webs are usually made at night and removed early in the morning. The spider rest on the vegetation. In some species distinct retreats are made close to the web. The spiders are very commonly found in grassland and savanna in low vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: The African species was revised by Grasshoff (1986).

Orb-web Photo A. Jones

Neoscona subfusca Photo P. Webb

Neoscona moreli orb-web Photo A. Jones

Neoscona rufipalpis Photo P. Webb

Neoscona alberti (Strand, 1913)

COMMON NAME: Albert's Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1913) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo as *Aranea alberti*. It has been sampled from five African countries and is possibly under collected, suspected to occur in more countries in-between. In South Africa, the species is known from two provinces (EOO=24 260 km²; AOO=16 km²; 552-2826 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Kenya, Rwanda, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48) (Natal Museum); Drakensberg (Injasuti) (-29,18, 29.42) (Natal Museum).

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web species that builds orb-webs in vegetation at night, removing the webs early in the morning. Known from the Grassland and Thicket biomes (Haddad et al. 2013). The orb-web of the specimen from Grahamstown was made in *Spartina* grass (Grasshoff 1986).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020) and Giant's Castle Nature Reserve. There are no known threats to the species.

Tibia 1-11.

Habitus and epigyne after Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona alberti female from Addo NP Photo L. Wiese

Neoscona alberti female ventral view Photo P. Webb

Neoscona angulatula (Schenkel, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Schenkel (1937) from Madagascar as *Araneus angulatulus*. The species has been recorded from five African countries. It is not very common in South Africa, and has been recorded only from KwaZulu-Natal within two protected areas. Due to its wide global geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Aldabra and Assumption, Kenya, Madagascar, Seychelles. New record: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: uMkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66).

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web species which builds orb-webs at night in vegetation, known from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in two reserves: uMkuzi Game Reserve and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015). There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Epigyne and habitus after Grasshoff (1986)

Tibia 1-11.

Neoscona angulatula Photo P. Webb

Neoscona blondeli (Simon, 1885)

COMMON NAME: Blondel's Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1885) from Liberia and known throughout Africa. The species is distributed widely in South Africa and has been recorded from all the provinces (EOO=1 071 783 km²; AOO=416 km²; 1-2 826 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa. Sampled from Swaziland, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alexandria (-33.65, 26.4); Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Lusikisiki (-31.37, 29.57); Port St. Johns Umngazi Mouth (-31.63, 29.53); Qachas Nek (-30.12, 28.68). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein (Farm Deelfontein) (-30.98, 23.81); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65); Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Gauteng:** Hekpoort (-25.9, 27.61); Melville Koppies (-26.17, 27.99); Poortview, Roodepoort (-26.15, 27.89); Pretoria/Tshwane following localities: Villieria (-25.71, 28.23), Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2), Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Amanzimtoti (-30.04, 30.88); Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27), Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76), St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41), Mapelane Nature Reserve (-28.39, 32.42), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Hillcrest (-29.77, 30.72); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Illovo Beach (-30.12, 30.85); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Mtubatuba (-28.4, 32.18); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1);

Tibia 1-11.

Habitus after Grasshoff (1986)

N. blondeli female of Wakkerstroom Photo P. Webb

N. blondeli female from Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona blondeli (continued)

Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76); Umgeni River (-29.26, 30.32); Umkomaas (-30.2, 30.8); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79).

Limpopo: Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Nylstroom/ Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/ Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Swadini Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Noordkaap (-25.66, 31.07); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Pilgrims Rest (-24.89, 30.75). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Swaruggens (Farm Olivenkloof) (-25.54, 26.52); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Hopetown (Farm Suffolk) (-29.58, 24.24); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Brackenfeld Nature Reserve (-33.9, 18.72); Durbanville (-33.83, 18.66); Grootvadersbos (-26.5, 28.36); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Robben Island (-33.8, 18.35).

LIFESTYLE: A very common orb-web species, which builds webs in vegetation at night and removes them early in the morning. Sampled from all the floral biomes except the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also found in crops such as avocado, cotton, pecans, pistachio, tomatoes and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Present in >20 protected areas such as the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Makalali NR (Whitmore et al. 2001); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona blondeli female from Alberts Falls Photo J. van Zyl

Neoscona blondeli immature female from Kloof Photo P. Webb

Neoscona blondeli Woodbush Photo P. Webb

Neoscona chiarinii (Pavesi, 1883)

COMMON NAME: Chiarini's Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pavesi (1883) from Ethiopia as *Epeira chiarinii*. The species is known from eight African countries. It is not very common in South Africa and has only been recorded from two provinces so far. Due to the wide geographical range in Africa, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Burundi, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Rwanda, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Uganda. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Mpumalanga:* Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1).

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web spiders. They make orb-webs at night in vegetation and removed it early in the morning. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009). There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona hirta (C. L. Koch, 1844)

COMMON NAME: Large Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1844 as *Epeira hirta* with type locality only as "Süd Africa". The species is known from seven African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from six provinces (EOO=728 509km²; AOO=100km²; 7-1758m a.s.l.) including eight protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Botswana, Ivory Coast, Swaziland, Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); King William's Town (Pirie Forest) (-32.88, 27.39); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (-26.20, 28.04); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **Limpopo:** Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.99, 18.43); Waenhuiskrans (-34.66, 20.23); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Wellington (-33.65, 19); Robben Island (-33.79, 18.37); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Grootbrakrivier Kouma Nature Reserve (-34.03, 22.22); Bontebok National Park (-34.06, 20.46); Waenhuiskrans (-34.66, 20.23).

LIFESTYLE: Females of this large species (11-17 mm) make orb-webs at night in vegetation and remove the web early in the morning. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also found in vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013). The species is also associated with the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* trees in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad 2015).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Sampled from 10 protected.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Epigyne Photo C. Haddad

Neoscona hirta female from Aardvark NR
Photos P. Webb

Neoscona kivuensis Grasshoff, 1986

COMMON NAME: Kivu Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Grasshoff (1986) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species is also recorded in South Africa from two provinces. There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: The Democratic Republic of the Congo. **New: South Africa.**

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23?). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: The species makes orb-webs at night and removes them early in the morning. Sampled from the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Rooipoort Nature Reserve and Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona kivuensis Photo E. Klimsa

Abb. 161. — M. (Araneae) *kivuensis* n. sp. ♂ Tibia I-II. — MT 134

After Grasshoff (1986)

Epigyne Photo C. Had-

Neoscona kivuensis male from Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona moreli (Vinson, 1863)

COMMON NAME: Morel's Grass Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Vinson (1863) from Reunion as *Epeira morelii*. The species has a wide global distribution and is known from the Afrotropical Region, Cuba and Argentina. In Southern Africa, it is recoded from Botswana and South Africa. It is found in all nine provinces of South Africa and occurs in more than 10 protected areas (EOO=838 434 km²; AOO=232 km²; 12 020 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cuba, Argentina and wide spread throughout Africa and Seychelles. The species is recorded from Swaziland and all nine provinces of South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Fort Grey Nature Reserve (-33.19, 27.12); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37). **Free State:** Clarens (Farm Adullam) (-28.51, 28.43); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Fouriesburg (Mooifontein) (-28.61, 28.23); Golden Gate Nature Reserve (-28.5, 28.62); Ventersburg (-28.08, 27.14). **Gauteng:** Bon Accord (-25.62, 28.2); Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Centurion (Irene) (-25.85, 28.16); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Moloto (-25.46, 28.63); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.85, 28.16); Dinokeng (-25.4, 28.38). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Ngoye Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval)(-27.35, 31.61); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Kamberg Nature Reserve, Fernwood Field Centre (-29.39, 29.67). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Meetsa-A-Bophelo Mission Station (-24.25, 30.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47).

Neoscona moreli female from Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona moreli male from Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona moreli female from Dinokeng Photo P. Webb

Neoscona moreli (continued)

Mpumalanga: Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (26.08, 28.57); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Hendrina (-26.15, 29.71);); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Noup (-30.13, 17.2). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park(-32.28, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a very common grassland species that makes its web at night and removes it early in the morning. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from avocado, pecans and pistachio orchards, and cotton, lucerne, maize and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Sampled in >10 protected areas such as: Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Makelali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001); Polokwane NR (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2015).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona moreli female in web from Mpetsane Photos A. JAones

Neoscona moreli female dorsal and ventral view from Mpetsane Photos A. JAones

Neoscona novella (Simon, 1907)

COMMON NAME: Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species that was described by Simon (1907) as *Araneus novellus* from Bioko. It was also collected from South Africa. From South Africa it is known from five provinces, including three protected areas (EOO=381 323km²; AOO=24km²; 62-1369m a.s.l.). Because it occurs over a large area it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Bioko. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76 24.81). **Limpopo:** Mogalakwena Nature Reserve (-22.725, 28.7753); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27). **North West:** Zeerust (-25.533, 26.083). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Game Reserve (-28.561, 24.162). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West, Farm 394 (-32.57, 22.99); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: Small orb-web spiders. They make orb-webs in the vegetation at night and remove them early in the morning. Sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna and Nama Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve, Mogalakwena Nature Reserve and Rooipoort Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known only from the female.

Habitus and epigyne after Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona novella female from Cape Town
Photos P. Webb

Neoscona penicillipes (Karsch, 1879)

COMMON NAME: Large Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Karsch (1879) as *Epeira penicillipes*, with a wide global distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa it has been sampled from eight of the provinces including eight protected areas (EOO= 891 770 km²; AOO=68 km²; 16-1651 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout West and Central Africa. **New: South Africa.**

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91). **Free State:** Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Kemptonpark (Esther Park) (-26.1, 28.2); Rietvleidam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Irene, Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Tshulu, Venda (-22.58, 30.81); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Soutpansberg (-31.04, 20.04). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **North West:** Swarttruggens (Farm Olivenkloof (373 JP)) (-25.54, 26.52). **Northern Cape:** Noup (-30.13, 17.2). Rooipoort Game Reserve (-28.561, 24.162).

LIFESTYLE: Large orb-web spiders (11 - 22 mm). They make orb-webs at night in the vegetation. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna, Succulent and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species is also associated with the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* trees in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad 2015).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in >8 protected areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009) and Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Mpetsane Conservation Estate (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021).

Neoscona penicillipes female Photo P. Webb

Neoscona penicillipes male Photo P. Webb

Neoscona penicillipes female Photo P. Webb

Epigyne Photo ASD

After Grasshoff (1986)

Abb. 115. — N. (Araneus) penicillipes. ♂ Tibia I-II, PhnU 1728.

Neoscona quadrigibbosa Grasshoff, 1986

COMMON NAME: Four-humped Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Grasshoff (1986) from Namibia. It is presently known from four African countries. This species is possibly under-collected and suspected to occur in more countries in the intervening range. From South Africa it has only been collected from a protected area in Limpopo. (EEO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 542 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide global geographic range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, Namibia, Swaziland. **New: South Africa.**

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo:* Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93).

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web spiders. They make orb-webs in the vegetation at night. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona quincasea Roberts, 1983

COMMON NAME: Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Roberts (1983) from the Aldabra Atoll. It is recorded from eight countries in the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa, the species is recorded from seven provinces and occurs in more than 10 protected areas (EOO=659 437 km²; AOO=80 km²; 54-1557 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Aldabra & Assumption, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Namibia, and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Tswaing Crater Nature reserve (-25.42, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93). **Mpumalanga:** Machadodorp (-25.66, 30.26); Barberton, Montrose Mine (-25.79, 31.04); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84). **Western Cape:** Elgin (-34.16, 19.06); Fish Hoek (Peer Hill) (-34.05, 18.35); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); Kamanassie Nature Reserve (-33.66, 23.12); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85).

LIFESTYLE: These small species (4.5--7.0 mm) makes orb-webs in the vegetation at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species is also sampled from pine plantations and vineyards. The species is also associated with the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* trees in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad 2015).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from >10 protected areas such as: Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009).

After Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona quincasea female Photo Peter Webb

Neoscona quincasea male Photo Peter Webb

Neoscona rapta (Thorell, 1899)

COMMON NAME: Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Thorell (1899) as *Aranea rapta* from Cameroon. It has a wide global distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa, the species is recorded from eight provinces including nine protected areas (EOO=775 796 km²; AOO=72km²; 4-1557m a.s.l). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kenton-on-Sea (-33.68, 26.67); Silaka Nature Reserve (-31.62, 29.49). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51,25.25). **Gauteng:** Centurion (Irene, Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Gate (-28.1, 32.45); Wetland Park: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Wetland Park; uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45). **Limpopo:** Goro Game Ranch (22.99, 29.43); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27). **North West:** Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts) (-29.68, 22.74). **Mpumalanga:** Machadodorp (Elandshoogte Pine Plantation) (-25.66, 30.26). **Western Cape:** Lebanon Forest Station (-34.14, 19.04); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85).

LIFESTYLE: The species (7--8 mm) makes orb-webs in the vegetation at night. Sampled from all the floral biomes except the Desert and Succulent biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in seven protected areas: Silaka Nature Reserve; Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie et al. 2013); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve; Kosi Bay Nature Reserve; Ngome State Forest; uMkuze Game Reserve and Kgaswane Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona rapta female Photo I. Anderson

Neoscona rapta female Photo L. Wiese

After Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona rufipalpis (Lucas, 1858)

COMMON NAME: Green Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Lucas (1858) as *Epeira rufipalpis* from Gabon. The species has a very wide global distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa it is known from seven of the provinces including seven protected areas (EOO=720 049 km²; AOO=140 km²; 7-1556 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Gabon, St Helena, Tanzania, Togo, Yemen and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspruit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); 25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Waterkloof Ridge (-25.75, 28.3). **IRENEKwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Cape Vidal) (-28.16, 32.56); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29.00, 29.87); Lake Bangazi (-27.39, 32.38); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Hanglip Forest (-23.04, 29.91); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Nylstroom /Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Glenwood (-29.87, 30.98); Hazyview (-25.03, 31.12); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Broederstroom (-25.78, 27.87); Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Bredasdorp (-34.53, 20.04); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03); Sedgfield (-34.03, 22.81); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

LIFESTYLE: Large (11–13 mm) orb-web spiders. The orb-webs have widely-spaced spirals of very sticky, bright yellow silk which is monitored by the spider from within a tightly woven retreat of vegetation (usually leaves), held together with strong pale-yellow, non-sticky silk. Unusually amongst medium-sized members of the genus, some individuals are active even in mid-winter, repairing their webs if they are removed or broken and dealing with any prey that becomes trapped in the web. Other individuals seem to simply rest during the coldest and driest months, reappearing as the warmer weather of spring brings out more insects.

Neoscona rufipalpis female from Addo NP Photo L. Wiese

Neoscona rufipalpis male Photo I. Young

Neoscona rufipalpis female Photo P. Webb

Neoscona rufipalpis female ventral view Photo P. Webb

Neoscona rufipalpis (continued)

They make orb-webs in the vegetation at night. The spider lives in a funnel retreat made of silk between leaves on vegetation. The orb-web is made in front of the retreat. Silk threads have a golden shine. They are very commonly found in broad-leaved trees. Sampled from most of the floral biomes except the Desert, and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from avocado, citrus and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from seven protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

After Grasshoff (1986)

Retreat between leaves weaved together

Tightly woven retreat of vegetation

Neoscona rufipalpis female feeding Photo P. Webb

Small orb-webs have widely-spaced spirals Photos C.I. Strumpher

Neoscona subfusca (C.L. Koch, 1837)

COMMON NAME: Common Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Koch (1837) as *Atea subfusca* from Greece. A species with a very wide global distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region, Southern Europe and the near East. In South Africa, the species is very abundant and known from all nine provinces, and occurs in more than 40 protected areas (EOO=1 156 972km²; AOO=544km²; 1-2 826m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Distributed widely in Africa, Southern Europe and the near East.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Cwebbe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Fish River (-33.6, 26.85); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kenton-on-Sea (-33.68, 26.67); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Clarens (-28.51, 28.43); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.92, 27.58); Edenville (Farm Lusthof) (-27.55, 27.66); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23); Golden Gate Nature Reserve (-28.5, 28.62); Harrismith (-28.27, 29.13); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.2); Soetdoring Nature Reserve (-29.05, 26.21); Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48, 29.01); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.4); Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Centurion (Irene) (-25.87, 28.22); Diepsloot 388JR (-25.93, 28.02); Hekpoort (-25.9, 27.61); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Krugersdorp/Mogale (-26.09, 27.78); Magaliesburg (-25.99, 27.54); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Norscott Nature Reserve (-26.2, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Randfontein (-26.17, 27.7); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Pretoria/Tshwane (Capital Park) (-25.72, 28.19); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Rietveldam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Spieskloof Nature Reserve (-26.42, 28.46); Springs (-26.25, 28.43). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bulwer (-29.79, 29.77); Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Drakensberg Garden (-29.75, 29.25); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27), Fanie's Gate (-28.1, 32.45), Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48);

Neoscona subfusca female of Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona subfusca male from Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona subfusca female from Aardvark NR Photo P. Webb

Neoscona subfusca (continued)

Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); (Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.39, 29.67); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26); Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07); Victoria (-30.43, 30.5); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Bandelierkop (-23.31, 29.79); Soutpansberg (Bergpan) (-23.39, 30.94); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Ellisras/Lephalale (-23.67, 27.71); Entabeni Forest, (-23, 30.23); between Warmbath/Thabazimbi (Farm Elandsberg) (-24.73, 27.72); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Malta Forest (-23.82, 30.16); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Swartbos Forest (-23.53, 29.59); Tongwane (-24.22, 29.9); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Zanzibar Border Post (-22.57, 28.45). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Belfast (-25.69, 30.04); Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); D.R. de Wet Forest Reserve (-25.1, 30.78); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1); Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98); Glenwood (-29.87, 30.98); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Klingbiel Nature Reserve (-25.09, 30.46); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Pilgrims Rest (-24.89, 30.75); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78); Waterval Boven (-25.63, 30.32). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.53, 20.29); Kalahari Gemsbok National Park (-29.48, 25.24); Klein Papkuil Farm (-28.48, 23.72); Olifantsnekdam (-25.8, 27.25); Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Suffolk Farm nr Hopetown (-29.58, 24.24). **Western Cape:** Bredasdorp (-34.53, 20.04); Ceres (-33.36, 19.31); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Elgin (-34.16, 19.06); Paarl (-33.71, 18.98); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Fish Hoek (Peer Hill) (-34.05, 18.35); Gouritsmond (Borrelfontein) (-34.34, 21.87); Grootvadersbos (-26.5, 28.36); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Murraysburg (-31.96, 23.75); Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53); Saldanha (-33.01, 17.93); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.35, 21.67); Tygerberg Nature Reserve (-33.9, 18.65).

Epigyne Charles Haddad

Neoscona subfusca females from Irene Photos P. Webb

Neoscona subfusca (continued)

LIFESTYLE: This medium sized (4,5 - 10,5 mm.) species makes orb-webs in the vegetation at night and removes the web early in the morning and rest on plants. It is sampled from all the floral biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from crops such as avocado, citrus, grapefruit, macadamia, pecan and pistachio orchards, pine plantations, cotton, tomatoes and vineyards. The species is also associated with the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* trees in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad 2015) and *Ochna pulchra* trees in the Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from >20 protected areas such as Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Makelali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona subfusca female of Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona theisi theisiella (Tullgren, 1910)

COMMON NAME: Theis' Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Tullgren (1910) as *Aranea theisiella* from Tanzania. It has a very wide distribution throughout Africa. From South Africa it is known from seven provinces (EOO=530 158 km²; AOO=72km²; 38-1556m a.s.l.). Due to the wide global distribution of the species it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: West, Central, East Africa, Yemen, Mozambique. New: South Africa and Swaziland.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Citrus Research Station (-33.55, 25.69); Addo Elephant National Park-33.32, 25.72). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Irene, Gem Village Field (-25.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Midlands, Good Hope plantation, Boston (-29.651, 29.976); Mlawula Nature Reserve (-26.22, 32.00); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.544, 32.155); Pongola Nature Reserve (-27.369, 31.845). **Limpopo:** Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.24); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.162, 30.254); Lephalele/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Polokwane Game Reserve (-23.967, 29.467). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** George (-33.95, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: Medium sized (6,5 -10,5 mm) orb-web spiders. They make large orb-webs in the vegetation at night. They remove the web early in the morning and rest on plants. They are commonly sampled from the Thicket, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from seven protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona theisi theisiella male from Irene
Photo P. Webb

Neoscona theisi theisiella female from Irene
Photos P. Webb

After Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona triangula (Keyserling, 1864)

COMMON NAME: Red spotted Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described in 1864 as *Epeira triangula* from Mauritius. It has a very wide global distribution, known from Africa to India. In South Africa, the species is recorded from all nine provinces (EOO=1 117 557km²; AOO=304 km²; 7-1781 m a.s.l.) and occurs in more than 20 protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cape Verde to India and with a wide distribution throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Coega (-33.76, 25.65); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.90); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kasouga (-33.63, 26.43); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **Free State:** Bethlehem (-28.23, 28.3); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Deneysville (-26.87, 28.09); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.2); Philippolis (-30.25, 25.27); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Welkom (-27.97, 26.74); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Brakpan (-26.23, 28.37); Centurion (Irene) (-25.85, 28.16); Dunnottar (-26.35, 28.47); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Maraisburg (-26.11, 27.56); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Witwatersrand Botanical Gardens (-26.2, 28.04). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ashburton (-29.60, 30.38); Botha Hill (-29.48, 30.50); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve, farm Goschen (-29.97, 29.46); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Lake Sibayi (-27.35, 32.7); uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola (Farm Vergeval), district Ngotsche (-27.35, 31.61); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Sodwana Bay National Park) (-27.4, 32.76); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Bela-Bela (Highland Estate) (-24.83, 28.17); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46).

Neoscona triangula female ventral view Photo L. Oates

Neoscona triangula female Photo A. Eichhoff

Neoscona triangula female in web Photo I. Anderson

Neoscona triangula female from Irene Photo P. Webb

Neoscona triangula (continued)

Mpumalanga: Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98); Komatipoort (Farm Sommerreg 17 kmSE) (-25.53, 31.82); Kriel (-26.25, 29.26); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Kameeldrift (-29.38, 23.8); Kleinsee (-29.67, 17.07). **Western Cape:** Bellville (-33.9, 18.63); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Fish Hoek (Peer Hill) (-34.05, 18.35); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Knysna (-34.03, 23.0); Murraysburg (-31.96, 23.75); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.35, 21.67); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

LIFESTYLE: A large species (9 - 17 mm) that make orb-webs in the vegetation at night and removes them early in the morning, resting on plants during the day. It is very common in gardens during the summer season. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from crops such as avocado, macadamia and pecans orchards, onion, sorghum and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from *Burkea africana* in Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from >20 protected areas such as Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Mpetsane Conservation Estate Jones and Dippenaar-Schoeman 2022) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

After Grasshoff (1986)

Epigyne Anka Eichhoff

Neoscona triangula female ventral view
Photo Anka Eichhoff

Neoscona triangula female in web Photo Allen Jones

Neoscona triangula female in web Photo Allen Jones

Neoscona vigilans (Blackwall, 1865)

COMMON NAME: Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Blackwall (1859) as *Epeira hispida*, although the name was preoccupied and a replacement name was provided by Blackwall (1865). This is a species with a very wide global distribution, known from Africa to the Philippines and New Guinea. It is recorded from five provinces in South Africa (EOO=393 164 km²; AOO=60 km²; 51-1415 m a.s.l.) including four protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa to the Philippines and New Guinea.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mzimhlava River Mouth (-31.37, 29.58). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane: Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19), Welgegund (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.76, 28.22). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Greytown (-29.05, 30.60); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Kosi Bay Nature Reserve) (-26.93, 32.87); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Tugela Ferry (-28.74, 30.44); Good Hope Plantation, Boston (-29.651, 29.976). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Piet Retief (-27, 30.79). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: A large (11 - 16 mm) species making orb-webs at night in the vegetation. The webs are removed early in the morning. They rest on plants during the day. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in four protected areas such as Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona vigilans female from Ezemvelo Nature Reserve Photo P. Webb

Epigyne ASD

Neoscona vigilans female from Irene Photo P. Webb

After Grasshoff (1986).

GENUS *NEPHILINGIS* Kuntner, 2013

Nephilingis Kuntner, 2013 is represented by four African species.. The genus was transferred from Nephilidae to Araneidae by Dimitrov et al. (2017).

COMMON NAMES: Hermit spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Nephilingis cruentata* (Fabricius, 1775)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 20—25 mm, male 8--9 mm. The *Nephilingis cruentata* female is recognisable by her body shape and colour pattern. Carapace: dark, longer than wide; eyes in two evenly spaced rows; sternum distinct bright yellow. Abdomen: ovoid to cylindrical, varying from very dark with creamy-yellow anterior border to mottled grey-white with yellow anterior band; venter with four yellow spots.

LIFESTYLE: *Nephilingis cruentata* spins a white orb-web with a funnel retreat near the top. The web is frequently made on the outside of houses under the overhang of roofs.

TAXONOMY: Well documented.

Nephilingis cruentata female from Dlinza Photo Ant West

Nephilingis cruentata female from Hazyview Photo Annette van den Berg

Nephilingis cruentata female in retreat on tree Photo C. Haddad

Nephilingis cruentata (Fabricius, 1775)

COMMON NAME: Hermit Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A common widespread species found in Africa and South America. Sampled throughout tropical Africa. In the study area it is known from South Africa found mainly from the three eastern provinces and Swaziland and occurs in more than 10 protected areas (EOO=177 286 km²; AOO=116km²; 4-1415 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range, listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tropical South America, tropical and subtropical Africa, Indian Ocean Islands, Asia, Australia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ballito (-29.53, 31.21); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Greytown (-29.05, 30.6); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07); Umkomaas (-30.2, 30.8); Uvongo (-30.82, 30.39). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam)(-23.37, 29.32); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Meetsa-A-Bophelo Mission Station (-24.25, 30.45). **Mpumalanga:** Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.1, 30.78); Klingbiel Nature Reserve (-25.09, 30.46); Malelane (-25.49, 31.5); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

LIFESTYLE: *Nephilingis cruentata* build an asymmetrical white orb-web made, often against tree trunks, walls or large rocks with a funnel-shaped retreat on the side. They are frequently found under the overhangs of roofs. The webs are large (1-1.5m) orb-webs. It has been sampled from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in eight protected areas such as Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kuntner (2007), known from both sexes.

Nephilingis cruentata female from Ndumo NR
Photo Peter Webb

Nephilingis cruentata female from Nelspruit
Photo Aart Louw

Nephilingis cruentata female ventral view
Photo Les Oates

GENUS *PARALARINIA* Grasshoff, 1970

Paralarinia represented by four species endemic to Africa. Only one species known from South Africa

COMMON NAMES: Grass Orb-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Paralarinia denisi* (Lessert, 1938)

MORPHOLOGY: Grasshoff provided very little information on the genus morphology, only information on the genitalia available.

Translated from Lessert (1933) for *P. bartelsi*. Yellow-brown cephalothorax, with almost entirely dark cephalic region. Eyes located on black spots. Brown sternum, adorned with blackish marginal spots. Brown mottled and banded legs of brown-black: a wide ring at the end of the anterior femora and all protarsi. Greyish yellow abdomen; adorned with a distinct folium, with scalloped edges and finely white border; folium is bounded forward by two oblique spots converging forward and adorned back, on the longitudinal midline, with three lighter spots. Brownish ventral region, marked by 3 black longitudinal lines. back.

LIFESTYLE: Unknown.

TAXONOMY: The genus was erected by Grasshoff, 1970.

Paralarinia bartelsi female Photo Peter Webb

Paralarinia bartelsi (Lessert, 1933)

COMMON NAME: Bartels' Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lessert (1933) as *Larinia bartelsi* from Umbilo in KwaZulu-Natal. Known from three provinces including three protected area, De Hoop Nature Reserve, Isandlwana Nature Reserve and Tsitsikamma National Park (EOO=176 374 km²; AOO=24 km²; 71-1199 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffreys Bay (-34.04, 24.94). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Isandlwana Nature Reserve (-28.358, 30.651). **North West:** Mooinooi (-25.75382, 27.55839). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52).

LIFESTYLE: The species is an orb-web dweller that constructs typical orb-webs in and between vegetation at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Species protected in three protected areas such as De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Tsitsikamma National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1970). Known from both sexes.

Habitus after Grasshoff 1970

Paralarinia bartelsi female from Mooinooi dorsal and ventral view Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *PARAPLECTANA* Brito Capello, 1867

Paraplectana described by Brito Capello (1867) is represented by thirteen species and subspecies known from Africa, India and the East.

COMMON NAMES: Ladybird Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Paraplectana thorntoni* (Blackwall, 1865)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females 11–16 mm. This genus is distinguished by their round body and bright colour. In contrast with the uniformly pale brown carapace, the abdomen is shiny with bright red, yellow or orange patches on a dark background, resembling a lady beetle. The round abdomen almost completely covers the carapace. Their thin legs are arranged around the carapace. Males still unknown.

LIFESTYLE: They make spanning thread webs at night (Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). Sampled in the Grassland, Fynbos and Savanna biomes.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Paraplectana sp. female from Port Elizabeth
Photo Martie Rheeder

Paraplectana sp. female Photo J. Barendse

Paraplectana walleri Photo G. Johnston

Paraplectana thorntoni Photo Les Oates

Paraplectana thorn-toni (Blackwall, 1865)

COMMON NAME: Thornton's Red Ladybird Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1865 as *Eurysoma thorn-toni* from Mozambique from a region through which the river Shire flows to its confluence with the Zambezi. The species is known from seven African countries. In South Africa, the species is rare but recorded from six provinces (EOO=407 708 km²; AOO=40 km²; 49-1303 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species, due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Ghana, Madagascar, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Yemen.
New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Kentani (-32.5, 28.32); Beechamwood (-32.35, 28.75); Willowvale (-32.26, 28.5); Fort Fordyce (-32.6786, 26.4883). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Estcourt (-29.01, 29.87); Pongola Nature Reserve (-27.35, 31.61). **Limpopo:** Polokwane/Pietersburg (-23.89, 29.46). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **Western Cape:** Garden Route National Park (-33.95, 23.64); Mossel Bay (-34.18, 22.12).

LIFESTYLE: They are known to build spanning thread orb-webs at night. During the day they rest on vegetation, resembling a ladybird beetle. It is part of a possible mimetic complex involving two tortoise beetles (*Chiridopsis suffriani* the "normal" form of *C. nigrosepta*) as well as ladybird beetles with similarity to *Cheilonomes lunata* (Heron, 2016). Found in the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Pongola Nature Reserve and Garden Route National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Paraplectana thorn-toni female Photo Les Oates

Paraplectana thorn-toni female Photo Les Oates

Paraplectana thorn-toni female from Polokwane Photo S. Dippenaar

Paraplectana walleri (Blackwall, 1865)

COMMON NAME: Waller's Ladybird Spiders

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Blackwall (1865) as *Eurysoma walleri* from Mozambique from a region through which the river Shire flows to its confluence with the Zambesi. The species is known from three African countries. In South Africa, it is recorded from three provinces including the Addo Elephant National Park (EOO=103 369 km²; AOO=16 km²; 219-1107 ma.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species, due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: West, Central and Southern Africa and Madagascar.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Greytown Albert Falls (-29.4361, 30.3882). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Badplaas, Vygeboom Dam (-25.95, 30.56); Sabi Sand Wildtuin adjacent to the Kruger National Park. **Western Cape:** Mosselbaai (-34.18, 22.12).

LIFESTYLE: The species makes spanning thread orb-webs at night (Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). They feed on moths. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013). It was also found in citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in three protected areas such as Sabi Sand Wildtuin (Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Paraplectana walleri from Albertsfall
Photos G. Johnston

Paraplectana walleri from Sabie Sand
Wildtuin in spanning web Photo M. Cooper

Paraplectana walleri from Vygeboomdam,
Badplaas Photo Paul van Rensburg

Paraplectana species

UNDETERMINED

Port Elizabeth Photo Martie Rheeder

Paraplectana sp. juvenile from Ermelo Photo Peter

From Zimbabwe resembles the ladybird *Cheilonomes sulphurea* and also a local Chrysomelid of the genus *Atechna* (H. Heron pers comm). Photo Meg Cumming

From Nelspruit Photo Dr Bedford

From Garden Route

GENUS *PARARANEUS* Caporiacco, 1940

Pararaneus is a genus described by Caporiacco, 1940 and is represented by five species from Africa and Madagascar.

COMMON NAMES: Spiky Field Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Pararaneus cyrtoscapus* (Pocock, 1898)

MORPHOLOGY: They resemble *Neoscona* species but they are decorated with more and stronger spines, especially the male. Their colour varies from dark brown to reddish yellow. In some species the shieldlike, dorsally rounded abdomen has a pair of small white spots and in most species there are four or five transverse bands over the abdomen. Their moderately long legs are the same colour as the carapace and bear strong spines, especially in males. Anterior protruding eyes are especially significant in males. The eyes are on tubercles.

LIFESTYLE: They make two types of webs: the mature spider makes a typical vertical orb web while the immature spiders make a horizontal web with a defective frame. It is cone-shaped with threads pulling the hub out of the plane of the frame. Three species have been recorded from South Africa.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Grasshoff (1968).

Pararaneus spectator female Photo Peter Webb

Pararaneus perforatus male from Woody Cape Addo NP
Photo Linda Wiese

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus (Pocock, 1898)

COMMON NAME: Spiky Field Spiders

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1898 as *Araneus cyrtoscapus* from type locality Estcourt in South Africa. The species has also been collected from six other African countries. In southern Africa, it occurs in Botswana, Zimbabwe and South Africa (EOO=891 952 km²; AOO=152 km²; 1-1593m a.s.l.). In South Africa, the species is known from eight provinces, and occurs in more than 10 protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species, due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Socotra, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Breakfast Vlei (-33.08, 26.95); Great Fish River Wetland Park (Farm Bucklands) (-33.48, 27.13); Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97); Queenstown (Farm Rookwood) (-32.08, 26.59); St. Francis, Thyspunt (-34.19, 24.82). **Free State:** Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Rietveldam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23); Rietveldam Nature Reserve Centurion (-25.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (Crocodile Farm) (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47), Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Verulam (-29.62, 31.06); Lake St. Lucia (-28.37, 32.23); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Midlands, Good Hope plantation, Boston (-29.651, 29.976). **Limpopo:** Balule Game Reserve (-24.29, 31); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Meetsa-A-Bophelo Mission Station (-24.25, 30.45); Pietersburg/ Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.416, 26.750); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger national Park, Punda Maria (-22.68, 31.01); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (20km SE) (-23.22, 31.56); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34). **Mpumalanga:** Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Kranspoort, near Loskopdam (-25.42, 29.43); Kruger National Park (Satara Camp) (-24.38, 31.78); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Vryburg (Farm Weltevrede) (-27.41, 24.51); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Table Mountain National Park. (-33.82, 18.48)

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus male Photo W. Schmidth

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus bdomens after Grasshoff (1986)

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus female Photo ASD

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus (continued)

LIFESTYLE: The species is an orb-weaver, with webs made in the field layer. The mature spider makes a typical vertical orb-web while the immature spiders make a horizontal web with a defective frame. It is cone-shaped with threads pulling the hub out of the plane of the frame. Commonly sampled with a sweep net from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes. Also sampled from avocado, citrus and pistachio orchards and tomato fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >13 protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus male palp
Photo A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Pararaneus cyrtoscapus female Photo Peter Webb

Pararaneus perforatus (Thorell, 1899)

COMMON NAME: Spiky Field Spiders

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1899 as *Aranea perforata* from Cameroon. The species is known also from the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Somalia and South Africa. In South Africa, the species is recorded only from the Eastern Cape. There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide global geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Somalia, Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84)

LIFESTYLE: The species is an orb-web, with webs made in the field layer. The mature spider makes a typical vertical orb-web while the immature spiders make a horizontal web with a defective frame. It is cone-shaped with threads pulling the hub out of the plane of the frame. Commonly sampled with a sweep net from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Pararaneus perforatus male and female
After Grasshoff (1986)

Pararaneus perforatus female from Bathurst Photo J. Richter

©JOANYOUNG2012

Pararaneus perforatus male Photo Joan Young

Pararaneus spectator (Karsch, 1885)

COMMON NAME: White Spot Spiky Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Karsch (1885) as *Epeira spectator*, with a wide global distribution including several countries in Africa and the Middle East. In South Africa it has been sampled from six of the provinces, and occurs in eight protected areas (EOO=407 674 km²; AOO=84 km²; 47-1762 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range of the species it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web spider with webs made in the field layer. Commonly sampled with a sweep net from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes. Also sampled from crops such as maize and strawberries.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread in Africa, Middle East.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **Free State:** Edenville (Farm Lusthof) (-27.55, 27.66). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit (Farm Onverwacht) (-25.8, 28.74); Halfway House (-25.99, 28.13); Hekpoort (-25.9, 27.61); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-26.14, 27.86); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.39, 29.67); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38). **Mpumalanga:** Bethal (-26.44, 29.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in eight protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

P. spectator female Photo Les Oates

Female Photo R. Steenkamp

Pararaneus spectator female Photo H de Klerk

Pararaneus spectator female Photo Peter Webb

Pararaneus spectator abdomens after Grasshoff (1986)

UNKNOWN SPECIES

Pararaneus species

Charles Haddad from KZN

GENUS *PASILOBUS* Simon, 1895

The genus *Pasilobus* is represented by 13 species and five species are known from Africa.

COMMON NAMES: *Pasilobus* Bird Dropping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Pasilobus bufoninus* (Simon, 1867)

MORPHOLOGY: *Pasilobus* has never been revised other than Simon's (1895) original generic description. Based on the latter, *Pasilobus* differs from *Paraplectana* by the presence of thickened lanceolate setae in the eye region; the median ocular quadrangle subquadrate and slightly raised; abdomen twice as broad than long, with low tubercles; legs quite slender, anterior and posterior legs longest; patellae, tibiae and metatarsi flattened and slightly unequal, metatarsi shorter than tibiae (Robinson & Robinson 1975).

LIFESTYLE: Spiders observed on the upper surfaces of leaves, fully visible during the day, strongly resembling bird droppings. The thin scattering of silk threads on the leaf surface surrounding the first observed specimen increased its resemblance to a bird dropping (Roff & Haddad 2015);

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Pasilobus dippenarae female Photo J. Roff

Pasilobus dippenarae egg sac Photo J. Roff

Pasilobus dippenarae Roff & Haddad, 2015

COMMON NAME: Dippenaar's Pasilobus Bird Dropping Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal Province endemic described in 1915 from Hilton College Nature Reserve. Also sampled from three other localities around Hilton and Pietermaritzburg (EOO=419 km²; AOO=16 km²; 634-1521m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic purposes.

LIFESTYLE: The species was observed during the day in the field while resting on the upper surfaces of leaves, fully visible during the day, strongly resembling bird droppings. It had made a thin covering of silk threads on which it was sitting. They were found about 2 m above the ground in leafy branches. They build a web at night close to bushes and small trees. The more-or-less horizontal web has a triangular frame that is divided into halves by a midline thread running from the apical angle to bisect the base. From the midline thread hang 4–11 pairs of widely spaced spanning threads; these are the only adhesive elements in the web. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Roff & Haddad 2015).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Cumberland Nature Reserve (- 29.512, 30.514); Gwen's Valley, Hilton College Nature Reserve (-29. 28, 30. 17); National Botanical Garden (-29.61, 30.35); Pietermaritzburg, Boughton (- 29.597, 30.323).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the National Botanical Garden. More sampling is needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Roff & Haddad (2015)

Pasilobus dippenarae female Photo J. Roff

Pasilobus dippenarae female with egg sac
Photo J. Roff

GENUS *POLTYS* C. L. Koch, 1843

The genus *Poltys* is represented by 43 species of which nine are known from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). Only one species has so far been recorded from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Poltys Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Poltys illepidus* C. L. Koch, 1843

MORPHOLOGY: *Poltys* is a rather distinctive araneid genus that can be recognised by a combination of widely separated lateral eyes and a pear-shaped carapace, where the “stalk” of the pear is an eye tubercle present as a frontally elevated projection. The median ocular quadrangle is as long as it is wide, the lateral eyes are widely separated and the median eyes are situated anterior on eye tubercles. Legs I and II are long with flat curved and spinulose tibiae and metatarsi. The large abdomen is anteriorly elevated and bears irregular tubercles.

LIFESTYLE: They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn. Adult males are small and do not make webs. Moths are the most frequent prey. The spiders are cryptically camouflaged and during the day they hide motionless on vegetation with the legs drawn tightly around the body and just protruding between the legs (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Poltys furcifer female from Tembe Elephant Park Photo Charles Haddad

Poltys furcifer female Photo Ian Riddell

Pollys furcifer Simon, 1881

COMMON NAME: Pollys Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1881) from Tanzania (Zanzibar). It has been collected also from Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa. The species is suspected to occur in more countries within this range. In South Africa, the species has been recorded from six provinces and five protected areas (EOO=355 839km²; AOO=48km²; 78-1556m a.s.l). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes dense orb-webs in vegetation at night. During the day they hide between the vegetation. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.5444, 32.1546). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Medikwe Heritage Site (-22.99, 29.61); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67). **Mpumalanga:** Schagen (-25.43, 30.8); Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009), Tembe Elephant Park, Ndumo Game Reserve, Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

GENUS *PRASONICA* Simon, 1895

The genus *Prasonica* described by Simon (1895) is represented by 10 species of which seven are from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Prasonica Leaf Weaver Orb-Web Spider/ African cucumber spiders.

TYPE SPECIES: *Prasonica albolimbata* Simon, 1895

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 7-10 mm, male 5-6 mm. Their pear-shaped carapace is narrower in the eye region, bears white setae and is a uniform green in live specimens. The median eyes are grouped together and the posterior median eyes are the largest. Lateral eyes are close together. An oval abdomen is slightly flattened above with varied yellow, white or dark brown colour patterns and white setae, sometimes posteriorly with black spots. Their legs are fairly long and the female has a very long scape, resembling the genus *Araniella*.

LIFESTYLE: The spider is mainly found on forest clearings, where it weaves its orb web between leaves and flowers. These webs are only about 10 cm in diameter. This spider is camouflaged by its green colour. They have been observed to weave a retreat in the fold of leaves. Freshly hatched spiderlings are red and change to brown.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Grasshoff (1971).

Prasonica seriata female Photo Peter Webb

Prasonica seriata female ventral view
Photo Peter Webb

Prasonica seriata female in retreat on
leaf Photo Peter Webb

Prasonica albolimbata Simon, 1895

COMMON NAME: Leaf weaver orb-web spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1895) from Madagascar. It has also been collected from three African countries and it is suspected to occur in more African countries. In South Africa, it is recorded from three provinces (EOO=143 468 km²; AOO= 24 km²; 67-1451 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes an orb-web in low vegetation and when not active it weaves a silk retreat below a leaf. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Madagascar, Yemen, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). *KwaZulu-Natal*: Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). *Limpopo*: Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Lephalale (-23.4, 28.05); Waller's Camp -22.424, 30.911). *Mpumalanga*: Loskopdam (-25.42, 29.43); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001) and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1971). Known only from female.

Prasonica albolimbata female Loskopdam Peter webb

Prasonica albolimbata female Loskopdam Photo Peter Webb

Prasonica albolimbata female Middelburg Photo Peter Webb

After Grasshoff (1971)

Prasonica nigrotaeniata (Simon, 1909)

COMMON NAME: Leaf weaver orb-web spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Simon (1909) as *Mangora nigrotaeniata* from Kenya. It has been collected from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa it has been sampled from four provinces, and is protected in the Pretoria National Botanical Garden (EOO=31 268 km²; AOO=20 km²; 526-1444 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range of the species it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web spiders. They make orb-webs in low vegetation. When not active they weave a silk retreat below a leaf. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: West, Central, East Africa and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene, Smuts House (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kloof (-29.79, 30.84). **Limpopo:** Lephale (-23.40, 28.05). **Mpumalanga:** KwaMhlanga (-25.43, 28.71).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Pretoria National Botanical Garden.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1971). Known only from female.

Prasonica nigrotaeniata female from Kloof Photo P. Webb

Abdomen after Grasshoff (1971)

Epigynum after Lessert (1933)

Prasonica nigrotaeniata female from Irene Photo P. Webb

Prasonica seriata Simon, 1895

COMMON NAME: African Cucumber Orb-web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic with type specimen described by Simon (1895) from Sierra Leone. It has been collected from Madagascar, Seychelles as well as in several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known from seven provinces (excluding Free State and Northern Cape) (EOO=554 429 km²; AOO=112 km²; 7-1902 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes an orb-web in low vegetation and when not active it weaves a silk retreat below a leaf. Sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread in Africa, Madagascar and Seychelles.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Hogsback Amatola Mountains (-32.59, 26.92); Keurkloof (Farm Ferndale) (Baviaanskloof) (-33.68, 24.83); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Qachas Nek (-30.12, 28.68); Cape St Francis, Thyspunt (-34.2056, 24.7083). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Highmoor (-29.3, 29.59); iSimangaliso Wetland park, uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve, South Boundary fence (-26.93, 32.32); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.0337, 32.4245); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.949, 29.87); Nylstroom/Modimolle Buffelspoort (-24.69, 28.4); Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.424, 30.911); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Tshulu Camp (Venda) (-22.579, 30.809). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop (-25.15, 31.2); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.01); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **North West:** Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in 15 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1971). Known from both sexes.

Prasonica seriata female Photo Peter Webb

Genitalia and habitus after Grasshoff (1971)

Prasonica seriata female Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *PYCNACANTHA* Blackwall, 1865

An African genus described by Blackwall (1865) and represented by four species (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Hedgehog Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781).

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 12–20 mm; male much smaller, distinct sexual dimorphism also in shape. Colour usually that of dry grass, varying from creamy yellow to pale brown; carapace slightly longer than wide, narrower in eye region; eyes eight in two rows (4:4); abdomen round, decorated with numerous sharply-pointed tubercles, abdomen overhangs the carapace; tubercles simple in *P. tribulus*; legs of medium length to long, anterior legs much longer than posterior ones, kept close to body when at rest.

LIFESTYLE: Hedgehog spiders are occasionally found in grasses and low vegetation. Their spiky bodies and colouration allow the spiders to blend in with grass, particularly *Themeda* and *Cymbopogon* species that have spiky seeds. The spiders rest on the grass during the day, and in the evening spin a triangular trapezium between two adjacent grass stems. Here they hang upside down, capturing flying insects. These spiders are suspected to produce mimetic pheromones that attract male moths, which they grasp with the forelegs before feeding. Sometimes prey is wrapped in silk before feeding commences. Egg sacs are attached to vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 1996).

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Pycnacantha tribulus female from Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

Pycnacantha tribulus female from Mooinooi Photo Peter Webb

Pycnacantha tribulus (Fabricius, 1781)

COMMON NAME: Hedgehog Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic species described in 1781 as *Aranea tribulus*, with the type locality given as “Cap bona spei”. Known from South Africa and Zimbabwe. In South Africa, it has a wide geographical distribution and is recorded from seven provinces, including more than 10 protected areas (EOO=1 000 757km²; AOO=136km²; 1-1758 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes reduced orb-webs. Both juveniles and adults make a suspended V-shaped trapezium at night, constructed between grasses or other low vegetation. The spider hangs from this trapezium and grasps its prey in flight. They feed mainly on moths and are suspected to produce chemicals mimicking the sex pheromones of moths. It was sampled in the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South African.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Fish River (-33.6, 26.85). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-28.9, 26.12); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.8, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Carletonville (-26.36, 27.4); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden (-26.08, 27.85). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Thanda Private Game Reserve (-27.87, 32.13); Midlands (-29.677, 29.922); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/ Mokopane (-24.17, 29). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Kruger National Park (-25.01, 31.97). **North West:** Dikhololo Nature Reserve (-25.5, 27.78); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

Pycnacantha tribulus female in trapezium web
Photo Les Oates

Pycnacantha tribulus female in trapezium web then with moth Photo Les Oates

Pycnacantha tribulus female with egg sac and newly hatched spiderlings Photos Les Oates

Pycnacantha tribulus (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from > 15 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Meise (1932). Known from both sexes.

Pycnacantha tribulus female in Photo Peter Webb

Pycnacantha tribulus female eye pattern Photo Peter Webb

After Simon 1895

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

Pycnacantha species

Jessica Kemper from Luderitz

SANSA VM

Immature or new sp.?? Peter Webb from Irene

GENUS *SINGA* C. L. Koch, 1836

The genus *Singa* is represented by 28 species of which four are known from Africa and two from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Singa Orb-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Singa hamata* (Clerck, 1757)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females and males 3–6 mm; male slightly smaller than female. Colour varies from cream to brown to greyish-black; carapace uniformly dark; carapace longer than wide; eyes eight in two rows (4:4); anterior median eyes largest, median ocular quadrangle wider in front than behind. Abdomen decorated with longitudinal stripes; oval, longer than wide, overhanging carapace; legs moderately long, kept close to body when at rest.

LIFESTYLE: Very little known about their behaviour. The small orb-webs are made in low-growing vegetation, herbs or grasses.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Singa albidorsata female Photo Peter Webb

Singa albidorsata female Photo A. Sharp

Singa albodorsata Kauri, 1950

COMMON NAME: Pyjama Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described in 1950 from the Kruger National Park, Mpumalanga. The species is also recorded from four provinces including five protected areas (EOO=155 735 km²; AOO=48 km²; 1-2185 m a.s.l.). Also sampled from Swaziland. There are no known threats to the species, it is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species constructs small orb-webs in low growing vegetation, herbs and grasses. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland, Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.66, 32.27); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.88, 32.25). **Limpopo :** Pafuri Waller's Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Pretoriuskop (-25.15, 31.2); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.123, 31.237).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in seven protected areas such as Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2011) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003). There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Singa albodorsata female Photo E. Klimsa

Singa albodorsata female Photo ASD

Singa albodorsata undescrbed male Photo ASD

Singa albodorsata epigynum Photo ASD

Singa lawrencei (Lessert, 1930)

COMMON NAME: Lawrence's Pyjama Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1930 from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. It is known also from Uganda and South Africa. In South Africa, the species has been collected in four provinces including seven protected areas (EOO=198 034 km²; AOO=40 km²; 93-1706m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species constructs small orb-webs in low growing vegetation, herbs and grasses. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Uganda and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Nylstroom/Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve(-25.72, 27.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in eight protected areas such as Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009). There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Singa lawrencei in web Photo P. Webb

Habitus after Lessert (1930).

GENUS *SINGAFROTYPA* Benoit, 1962

An endemic African genus represented by for four species. Only one species known from the Atlas Region (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Singafrotypa Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Singafrotypa acanthopus* (Simon, 1907)

MORPHOLOGY: Male unknown. Size: TL female 9–10 mm. They have elongated abdomen with parallel sides that overhang the spinnerets. Carapace dark brown, with wide cephalic region and widely separated median and lateral eyes; sternum dark brown; longer than wide. Abdomen elongate and cylindrical, longer than wide, caudally overhanging spinnerets

LIFESTYLE: Nothing known about their behaviour. Some specimen were sampled while sweeping grass.

TAXONOMY: Male unknown.

Singafrotypa mandela female dorsal and ventral view Photos Charles Haddad

Singafrotypa mandela female abdomen Photo ASD

Singafrotypa mandela Kuntner & Hormiga, 2002

COMMON NAME: Mandela's Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2002 from Cape Town. Known from three provinces (EOO=350 160 km²; AOO=16 km²; 9-1148 m a.s.l.) including two protected areas: Mkuze Game Reserve and Table Mountain National Park. The species is probably under collected and is suspected to occur in more localities. It is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Natural history unknown. *Singafrotypa* has a cylindrical body with advanced spinnerets might suggest utilization of rolled leaves or grass stems as a retreat on the web. Sampled from the Fynbos and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25). **Limpopo:** Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in Mkuze Game Reserve and Table Mountain National Park. There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Singafrotypa mandela epigynum female photo ASD

Singafrotypa mandela Photo J. Heymans

Singafrotypa mandela female photo Ernst Klimsa

GENUS *TRICHONEPHILA* Leach, 1815

The genus *Trichonephila* is represented by 38 species and subspecies. Four species known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Golden Orb-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Nephila pilipes* (Fabricius, 1793)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: sexually dimorphic, females 12–40 mm, males much smaller. Colour of each species is recognizable by its colour pattern, which may show considerable intraspecific variation; the abdomen is black with bright blue, red, yellow, silvery and/or white markings, legs sometimes banded or with a red hue; carapace: longer than wide, with short, hornlike protuberances in females of the larger genera; eyes eight in two evenly spaced rows; abdomen large, elongate and cylindrical; legs long and slender, two species (*Trichonephila fenestrata* and *T. senegalensis*) with conspicuous tufts of setae at least on tibiae of legs I, II and IV.

LIFESTYLE: *Trichonephila* species (golden orb-web spiders) build large (1–1.5 m) orb-webs between trees and shrubs. The viscid spiral of the web is yellowish and the radii are pulled out of their direct course to give it a notched appearance. The supporting lines are very strong and some resistance is felt when one wanders into them. The spiders make use of the same web over long periods, replacing only the viscid lines. In the older spiders the web may only be half a circle, while in the younger individuals the orb is more complete. Most nephilids practice genitalic mutilation, with the males breaking off the embolus during mating in an effort to plug the epigyne of females and prevent other males mating with her, a strategy that is not always successful. The egg clutches are surrounded by fine puffy silk and are usually laid near the web on surrounding vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014; Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010).

TAXONOMY: Revised.

Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis female Photo Johan van Zyl

Trichonephila fenestrata female Photo Peter

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata female Photo J. van Zyl

Trichonephila komaci female Photo Andre Coetzer

Trichonephila fenestrata Thorell, 1859

COMMON NAME: Black Legged Golden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Thorell (1859) from Caffraria (old name for Eastern Cape). The species is sampled also from Lesotho and Swaziland. In South Africa found in all the provinces and occurs in more than 20 protected areas (EOO=988 280km²; AOO=420 m²; 0-1795m a.s.l.). Due to wide range listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species make large, complete golden yellow coloured orb-webs between trees and shrubs. Sampled from all the biomes except the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013). It was also sampled in citrus and prickly pear orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland, Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Brakkloof (-33.53, 26.5); Fort Beaufort (-32.78, 26.62); Grahamstown (Tea Fountain) (-33.3, 26.52); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Keurkloof, Farm Ferndale (Baviaanskloof) (-33.68, 24.83); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Kirkwood (-33.39, 25.43); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Queenstown (Farm Rookwood) (-32.08, 26.59); Wilgerskloof Farm, Bamboesberg, Sterkstroom (-31.6, 26.37). **Free State:** Deneysville (-26.87, 28.09); Drakensberg Mountain Range (-24.62, 30.88); Edenville (Farm Lusthof) (-27.55, 27.66); Hoopstad (-27.85, 25.93); Kestell (-28.35, 28.72); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13). **Gauteng:** Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Hekpoort (-25.9, 27.61); Kemptonpark (Esther Park) (-26.1, 28.2); Krugersdorp/Mogale (-26.09, 27.78); Magaliesburg (-25.99, 27.54); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pyramid (-25.35, 28.37); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Wagon Drift (-33.52, 24.54); Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Creighton (-30.03, 29.83); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29.01, 29.87); Giant's Cup Wilderness Res., Farm Goschen (-29.97, 29.46); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7),

Trichonephila fenestrata female Photo Johann van Zyl

Trichonephila fenestrata female Photos P. Webb

Trichonephila fenestrata Thorell, 1859

Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.2). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Bosbokrand Nature Reserve (-24.84, 31.05); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Kampersrus (-24.48, 30.83); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park (Pafuri) (-22.46, 31.3); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Leydsdorp (-23.98, 30.53); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Louis Trichardt (-23.04, 29.91); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Ratombo Forest (-23.06, 30.17); Roodewal Forest (-23.02, 30.03); Soutpansberg (-31.04, 20.04); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58; 30.81); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27); Warmbath Dam (-24.87, 28.26); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Waterpoort (-22.54, 29.37); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95). **Mpumalanga:** Burgersfort (-24.68, 30.31); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78); Volksrust (-27.36, 29.88); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14); Waterval Boven (-25.63, 30.32). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Magaliesberg (-20.97, 31.65); Potchefstroom (-26.7, 27.09); Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22); Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **Western Cape:** Albertinia (-34.2, 21.59); Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63); Betty's Bay (-34.34, 18.94); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Constantia (-34.01, 18.44); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Fransmanshoek Conservancy (-34.3, 21.92); Gouritsmond (-34.34, 21.87); Heidelberg (-34.08, 20.95); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.99, 18.43); Noordhoek (-34.1, 18.37); Onrus (-34.41, 19.19).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >20 protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised known from both sexes.

Trichonephila fenestrata Photo Peter Webb

Trichonephila fenestrata female Photo W. Avni

Trichonephila fenestrata male Photo A. Jones

Trichonephila fenestrata Photo Peter Webb

Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis (Vinson, 1863)

COMMON NAME: Red Legged Golden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1863 from Madagascar. Known from several African countries. In South Africa it is known from three provinces (EOO=260 377 km²; AOO=68 km²; 7-1415 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: These spiders build large (1-1.5m) orb-webs. The viscid spiral of the web is yellowish golden. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Madagascar, Swaziland, Seychelles, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); (-28.3, 31.76); Melmoth (-28.57, 31.39); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76). **Mpumalanga:** Komatipoort, Farm Sommerreg (17 km SE) (-25.53, 31.82); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in six protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised, known from both sexes.

Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis female in web Photo Johan van Zyl

Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis female in web Photo Johan van Zyl

Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis female ventral view Photo Johan van Zyl

Trichonephila komaci Kuntner & Coddington 2009

COMMON NAME: Giant Golden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS:LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 2009 from KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from South Africa, Tanzania and Madagascar. In South Africa it is only recorded from a small area in KwaZulu-Natal. *Nephila komaci* is evidently rare (only 37 museum collections are known in addition to field searches). Due to wide geographical range it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free living web dwellers making large orb-webs in vegetation. Natural history mostly unknown. As with other *Trichonephila* species, *T. komaci* spin a large golden orb web, with a three dimensional barrier web at least in early instars. The two Tembe specimens were collected by beating a large shrub, thus the web was probably 2–4 m above the ground. Two other *Trichonephila* species (*T. inaurata*, *T. fenestrata*) are sympatric at Tembe. Sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania (Zanzibar), Madagascar, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Sodwana Bay (-27.56, 32.08); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in Tembe Elephant Park. There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised known from both sexes.

Epigynum Photo CH

Trichonephila komaci female in web at Tembe Elephant Park Photo Charles Haddad

Trichonephila komaci female in web at Ndumo GR Photo Charles Haddad

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata (Thorell, 1859)

COMMON NAME: Banded Legged Golden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS:LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic known from both sexes sampled from Swaziland, South Africa and Namibia. In South Africa commonly found throughout the country in all the provinces and occurs in more than 10 protected areas (EOO=797 170 km²; AOO=252 km²; 16-1864 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range, listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: These spiders build large (1-1.5m in diameter) orb-webs. The viscid spiral of the web is yellowish golden. Sampled from all the biomes except the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Wide throughout Africa. In study area known from Swaziland and South Africa (all 9 provinces).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Klipplaat (-33.01, 24.33); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Pearston (-32.59, 25.15). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Heilbron (-27.29, 27.97); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65); Vredefort (-27, 27.37); Welkom (-27.97, 26.74). **Gauteng:** Bon Accord (-25.62, 28.2); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Tswaing Crater (-25.42, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09; 32.1); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (-23.37, 29.32); Diphuti (-24.38, 30.66); Farm Elandsberg, between Warmbath/Thabazimbi (-24.73, 27.72); Gravelotte (-23.95, 30.57); Kampersrus (Farm Madrid) (-24.48, 30.9); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Leopard Creek Reserve (Farm Caledonia) (-23.83, 27.95); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Louis Trichardt (-23.04, 29.91); Mussina (-22.33, 30.03); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Ngala Game Reserve (-24.47, 31.35); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Phalaborwa, Grietjie Nature Reserve (-24.18, 31.65); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52);

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata female

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata female in yellow web Photo Peter Webb

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata female (bottom) and male (top) in web Photo Margaret Reid

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata (continued)

Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Timbavati Game Reserve (-24.42, 31.33); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.32); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Louw's Creek (-25.79, 31.04). **Northern Cape:** Gemsbok Pan (-29.47, 23.58). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22); Utopia Nature Reserve (-29.82, 27.48); Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Buffelsdrift (-33.69, 22.79); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Grootvadersbos (-26.5, 28.36); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Swartklip (-34.19, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >20 protected areas. There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised, known from both sexes.

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata female with egg sac Photo John Leroy

Trichonephila senegalensis annulata mating Photo C. Willis

GENUS *URSA* Simon, 1895

The genus *Ursa* is known from five species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Only one is known from South Africa, the rest of the species known from Vietnam and South America.

COMMON NAMES: Ursa Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Ursa pulchra* Simon, 1895

DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERS: Small spiders. Carapace pear-shaped; eyes in two rows; anterior and posterior median eyes close together; lateral and anterior median eyes larger than posterior lateral eyes. Abdomen round and decorated with faint whitish markings. Legs same colour as carapace; leg IV shortest; leg I with rows of lined setae.

LIFESTYLE: Nothing known about their behaviour. Some specimen were sampled while sweeping grass.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Ursa turbinata female from Irene Photos Peter Webb

Ursa turbinata Simon, 1895

COMMON NAME: Ursa Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1895) from Cape Town in the Western Cape. The species has been sampled from three provinces including (EOO=204 746 km²; AOO=12 km²; 34-1328 m a.s.l.). *Ursa* is an uncommon genus that might be listed in the unknowns in most collections. As identification is still problematic it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene Veldt (-25.89, 28.23). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: The behaviour of the species is unknown. The specimen have been sampled while sweeping grass in the Fynbos and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve. There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling needed

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Ursa turbinata female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Ursa turbinata female from Irene Photos Peter Webb

After Levi (2005)

UNDETERMINED SPECIES ??

GENUS *URSA* species

Species from Delmas Photo Peter Webb

Species from Irene Photo Peter Webb

From Soutpansberg

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

GENUS ZYGIELLA F. P.-Cambridge, 1902

The genus *Zygiella* is known from 11 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Species reported from South Africa still undetermined. It could be *Zygiella x-nota* a species with a very wide distribution range

COMMON NAMES: Zygiella Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Eucharia atrica* C.L. Koch

DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERS: Medium-sized spiders 5-8 body length. Carapace with black eye region; fovea distinct; carapace often with dark triangular mark and slender lines anterior to dorsal groove; eyes in two rows; eye region more compact. Abdomen smooth elliptical abdomen; abdomen silvery, with pattern of black patches arranged in two longitudinal rows superficially resembles that of representatives of *Enoplognatha* spp. Legs same colour as carapace; leg IV shortest; leg I with rows of lined setae. Epigynum lacking depressed posterior plate, with anterior margin broad, much thickened and darkened.

LIFESTYLE: Nothing known about their behaviour. Some specimen were sampled while sweeping grass.

TAXONOMY: South African species not yet named.

Zygiella x-nota a species with a very wide distribution range after Levi (2002)

Zygiella web

Female from Jeffreys Bay Photo Linda Wiese

Female from Potchefstroom Photos Jarrod Todd

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